

in Azolla color, multiplication, and death rate were calculated.

In summer, when water temperature rose to 28-30 °C with 100,000 lux and NH₄-N was 4-7 ppm, Azolla grew well. When NH₄-N was above 8 ppm, Azolla died. Azolla needed less NH₄-N at low temperatures and sunlight. In the spring propagating tent and winter greenhouse, Azolla died when NH₄-N was 4-5 ppm. It grew well when NH₄-N was 0.5-2 ppm in the winter greenhouse and 2-3 ppm in the spring propagating tent. □

Growth of azolla at different air temperatures, sunlight hours, and NH₄-N levels in Hebei, China.

Place	Hours Sunlight	Light force (Lux)	Av temp (°C)	NH ₄ -N ppm	Azolla condition
WPH ^a	5	0.05	7	3-4	Slowly died
WPH	7	0.5	15	4-5	Slowly died
NTH	7	0.5	15	3-4	Retarded growth
WPH	7	1	10	0.5-1.5	Good growth
SPT ^b	7	1	15	0.5-2	Good growth
SPT	8	0.8	10	5-7	Died
SPT	8	0.8	15	4-5	Quickly died
SPT	10	1	20	5-6	Quickly died
SPT	10	2	23	2-3	Good growth
SGP ^c	12	10	30	6-7	Good growth
SGP	12	10	30	8-12	Died
SGP	12	10	28	4-6	Good growth

^aWinter-passing house. ^bSpring propagating tent. ^cSummer growing pond.

Response of rice to *Azospirillum* inoculation

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Table 1. Effect of *Azospirillum* seed inoculation on seed germination and vigor index. Coimbatore, India.

<i>Azospirillum</i> isolate	Germination (%)	Vigor index	Increase (%)
	<i>CO 40</i>		
Sp. 7	92.0	1140	16.3
IPI	96.0	1680	71.4
S-3	94.0	1480	51.0
Untreated control	86.0	980	-
CD (P=0.05)	4.8	180	
	<i>IR50</i>		
sp. 7	97.0	1380	27.7
IPI	96.0	1440	33.3
S-3	92.0	1260	16.6
Untreated control	88.0	1080	-
CD (P=0.05)	3.2	148	

We studied the influence of inoculating seed of IR50 and Co 40 rice varieties with three strains of nitrogen-fixing bacterium *Azospirillum brasilense*: Sp. 7, Brazil; IPI isolated from root tissues of *Ipomoea* sp., India; and nonnitrogen-fixing *A. brasilense* mutant S-3, University of Florida, USA.

Seeds of IR50 and Co 40 were surface sterilized by soaking in sterile water for 12 h, separately inoculated with broth cultures of the bacterium strains, and dried in the shade. Each seed surface had an average 2.2×10^5 cells of the bacterium. The seeds were germinated at 30°C (paper towel method). Vigor index (shoot length + root length × % germination) was determined at 5 d.

In another experiment, inoculated seeds were sown in pots containing wet field soil. At 30 d after seeding,

seedling weight, root biomass, number of roots, and plant height were recorded.

Seed inoculation significantly increased germination and vigor index of both cultivars (Table 1).

In general, all three strains of *Azospirillum* enhanced seedling vigor. Shoot and root development, number of primary and secondary roots formed, and seedling weight increased significantly. Response was higher with IPI (Table 2).

Inoculation with S-3 also had positive effects. All three strains produced appreciable amounts of phytohormones *in vitro*, notably indoleacetic acid and gibberellic acid. This suggests that initial growth responses to inoculation might be due more to the secretion of growth-promoting substances than to biological N fixation. □

Table 2. Effect of *Azospirillum* inoculation on growth of 2 rice varieties.^a Coimbatore, India.

Treatment	CO 40				IR50			
	Shoot length (cm)	Root length (cm)	Primary roots (no.)	Dry wt (mg) of seedling	Shoot length (cm)	Root length (cm)	Primary roots (no.)	Dry wt (mg) of seedling
<i>Azospirillum</i> (Sp. 7)	16.34 a	6.20 a	5.80 a	74.0 ab	14.26 bc	5.80 bc	5.60 b	92.0 b
<i>Azospirillum</i> (IPI)	17.26 a	5.80 ab	5.33 a	80.0 a	18.20 a	6.48 c	6.90 a	112.0 a
<i>Azospirillum</i> (S-3)	16.20 a	5.20 b	5.20 a	68.0 b	19.20 a	5.40 a	4.20 cd	96.0 b
Uninoculated control	11.60 b	4.70 c	4.30 b	60.0 c	12.21 c	5.00 a	3.60 d	86.0 b
CD (P = 0.05)	2.27	0.69	0.81	6.7	2.26	0.76	0.93	10.9

^aFigures followed by the same letters are statistically similar.